

Quantum Decoherence

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There is interest in the literature in showing how quantum mechanics becomes classical mechanics in the high energy limit. For instance, in (1) it is argued that one may recover classical mechanics from quantum mechanics by restricting the range of k (momentum) in a Fourier series integral.

We have suggested in a previous note (2) that one may obtain the free particle quantum wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, from the classical requirement of conservation of momentum. This requires introducing a second variable x such that one has orthogonality, but this orthogonality does not necessarily require all of x space. For example, if \hbar/p is tiny compared to dx , a small classical length, then one may have orthogonality of relevant p values within dx .

We have suggested that quantum mechanics is more general than classical mechanics and given that it is based on $\exp(ipx)$, the crests and troughs do not necessarily disappear, but become so small (i.e. resolution is so high) that one does not need to worry about it (unless one has one dimensional reflection-refraction).

We argue that if one has $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and this forms a very high resolution set of crests and troughs in dx , then integrating just within dx $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a^*(p)a(p)$. If the dominant $a(p)$ values represent very close p values (within experimental error), then it seems that there is no reason not to assign a single p value to dx and to dispense with crests and troughs, but to state that one has infinite resolution which is what is done in classical mechanics.

Conservation of Momentum

In (2), we argued that the classical notion of conservation of momentum is a key idea which should arise naturally in a probabilistic description of classical particles. We argued that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ describes a uniform distribution of static particles which may be replaced with $\pm p$ pairs at each x . This then leads to $P(p)P(-p) = 1/L$, but one must also impose conservation of momentum. This requires an extra variable, x , and the notion of orthogonality and leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a free particle, constant p , kind of probability.

This probability is very general mathematically, and is associated with a wavelength \hbar/p , with \hbar being linked to photon physics. Two key relations are:

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((1a))$$

$$\text{and } \int dx \exp(ip_1x)\exp(-ip_2x) = 0 \text{ if } p_1 \neq p_2 \quad ((1b))$$

In ((1)), any x may be used, but in reality quantum particles are restricted to length scales which may seem infinite mathematically, but are finite. For example, a quantum oscillator deals with x ranging from minus infinite to infinite, but in reality this infinite distance may be replaced by a finite one which seems extremely large compared to the bound region length. In other words,

we argue that one must exhibit caution when considering that any x value may be used in ((1a)) and ((1b)). One needs an x range which ensures ((1a)) and ((1b)).

Following this idea, we argue that dx , which is considered a tiny length in classical physics, may actually represent an infinite length if \hbar/p is tiny with respect to dx . In such a case, ((1a)) and ((1b)) would hold within dx . Furthermore

$$\int (x \text{ in } dx) W^*(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a^*(p)a(p) \ \text{approx}=1 \quad ((2))$$

For very high resolution in $\exp(ipx)$ s, i.e. $W(x)$'s crests and troughs fit in dx , it seems that the p values of relevant $a(p)$'s should be very close in value. If one has a high resolution in $W(x)$, then it is dominated by p 's which create this resolution. Thus, within experimental error, one may suggest that:

(A) There is one p value in dx

(B) There is infinite resolution in dx . (This is not strictly true, but given that many crests and troughs of $W(x)$ fit within dx , this seems to be a good approximation.

This does not mean that the crests and troughs of $W(x)$ disappear, but rather that there is no need to describe the "infinite resolution" mechanism because there is no classical experiment which resolves beyond dx . We argue later that the crests and troughs do not disappear because otherwise one could not solve the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem.

We suggest that the conditions (A) and (B) force a kind of decoherence because a crest-trough description is no longer needed. One may simplify and use (A) and (B). Thus, we suggest that quantum mechanics is a more general theory than classical mechanics.

Other Approaches in the Literature

In (1), a different approach is used. It is suggested that one may use $\exp(ipx)$ s in a Fourier series, but that one should truncate this series, i.e. only use p 's in a certain range $(-p_0, p_0)$. It is then suggested that one recovers classical physics.

We have suggested that $W(x)$ with a very resolution of x , i.e. very sharp crests and troughs is only associated with p 's which match this resolution. Thus, we suggest that one is restricting p 's by suggesting that only a few very close p values matter within a dx range.

In (1), calculations are performed for wavepackets to show that quantum crests and troughs are no longer a major feature in this approach. We suggest that when the crests and troughs of $W(x)$ fit within dx (many of them) that quantum resolution is not needed as a description of the problem and one may simply as described above.

The Price of Classical Simplification

Even though one may simplify the quantum scenario to obtain the classical one, we suggest that there is a physical example which still demonstrates that quantum mechanics is the more general theory and that is one dimensional reflection-refraction of light.

In such a case, one assumes infinite resolution as there is a precise point at which n_1 (index of refraction) becomes n_2 . This is a classical viewpoint. This point may be set to $x=0$. Then even if many wavelengths fit within a dx , it is useless to solve this problem classically, One must use a wavelength approach and write:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3a)) \text{ and}$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

Here A is linked to an incident photon, B a reflected and C and refracted and all three have the same energy.

We point out that in the above problem, one uses $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$ even though these do not represent the full x range. In other words, $\exp(ip_2x)$ is restricted to $x>0$ which technically violates the quantum mechanical statement that one must have $\exp(ipx)$ for all x . We note that in the case of an infinite well potential, even though one has $\exp(ipave x)$ and $\exp(-ipave x)$ within the well, it is argued that mathematically, $pave$ appears, and that one may take a Fourier series of the step-functions associated with the well. In the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, it seems one is using exact p , $-p$ and p_2 values.

Thus, ultimately the quantum description is the more general one and solves problems which the classical approach cannot. In other words, there is no classical limit for the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem which has an analogue for a particle with rest mass, namely a constant V_1 for $x<0$ and a V_2 for $x>0$.

We thus suggest that classical mechanics is a simplification which omits some key physical features which are required by rarely, i.e. only in the case of the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem (and perhaps some other cases). There is no 2-slit interference device which fits in the classical dx and so this is not an issue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, may be thought of as a mathematical probability which enforces conservation of momentum through orthogonality in x . Formally, one does not require x to range through all of space for orthogonality. We suggest that the key ideas are to have: $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)=\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$ and orthogonality to enforce conservation of momentum.

If, for high energy, the crests and troughs of $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ have very high resolution, then they essentially represent p values which are very close to this resolution, i.e. \hbar/p values. Then, orthogonality exists within the dx region (which is like infinite to the sharp

resolution wavelengths. In such a case, $W^*(x)W(x)$ integrated within dx leads to $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p)=1$ and we suggest that the p values are all very similar. One does not experimentally require resolution greater than dx , so the crest-trough resolution is overkill and one may replace the quantum picture with a single p value (or $p, -p$) in dx . This is simplification which applies to a specific scenario.

Even in the classical world, one may have one dimensional reflection-refraction and one cannot replace quantum mechanics with classical mechanics in that case. The reflection and refraction probabilities may only be calculated using quantum mechanics and there is no notion of high energy levels for this problem. Infinite resolution is assumed in that n_1 changes to n_2 at a sharp point $x=0$. It seems that no assumptions are made about the incident, reflected and refracted wavelengths.

Thus, we suggest that classical mechanics follows from removing the crest-trough features of quantum mechanics, together with the averaging of time, i.e. p and $-p$ must occur at different times because one no longer uses a statistical viewpoint.

References

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